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MONITORING OF REHABILITATION OF PREGNANT WOMEN WITH INFLAMMATORY DISEASES OF MAXILLOFACIAL REGION

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Relevance. In a pregnant woman, against the background of altered reactivity and reduced resistance of the body, hidden odontogenic foci of infection can lead to such serious complications as periostitis, abscess, phlegmon, osteomyelitis, mediastinitis, etc.

Despite the sufficient number of dentists in consulting clinics, the quality of dental examination of pregnant women at the professional level is not fully carried out. This situation dictates the urgent need for effective ways to optimize the prevention and treatment of inflammatory diseases of the maxillofacial system in pregnant women in outpatient settings.

Purpose of research. To conduct a retrospective analysis of inpatient and outpatient rehabilitation of pregnant women with inflammatory processes of the maxillofacial system in the Department of adult surgical dentistry and the clinic of surgical dentistry of the TSDI clinic for the period 2017-2019.

Materials and methods. Based on archived data for 2017-2019, the clinic of adult surgical dentistry of TSDI analyzed 67 medical records of hospitalized pregnant women aged 19 to 44 years with odontogenic inflammatory processes of the maxillofacial region, and 128 outpatient records of pregnant women with inflammatory processes of the periapical tissues of the dental-maxillofacial system. Statistical analysis of medical histories depending on the severity of maxillofacial region inflammatory processes in different periods of pregnancy and performed surgical and conservative interventions of different localities was carried out.

Results. Within 3 years, 34 (51%) pregnant women were hospitalized with odontogenic phlegmons of the maxillofacial region of different localization; 17(26%) were hospitalized with odontogenic abscesses; 9(13%) had a spilled periostotomy; 5(7.5%) were treated with various infiltrations and acute serous lymphadenitis.

Based on the study of the results of biochemical analyses, it was found that out of 67(100%) hospitalized pregnant women, 99.5% had a decrease in the hemoglobin content in addition to a shift in the leukocyte formula. Of all patients, 38% had mild anemia, 43% had moderate anemia, and 18.5% of pregnant women had severe anemia.

Planning the time of reception by a dentist should be carried out, avoiding critical periods of pregnancy, i.e. moments of increased danger, when the most insignificant stimuli can lead to the tone of the uterus, cause its contractions and lead

to miscarriage or premature birth. Preterm birth was observed in 12.0% of all treated pregnant women.

In the polyclinic of surgical dentistry of TSDI, monitoring of pregnant women who applied in the period 2017-2019 was conducted. 128 outpatient records of pregnant patients with various forms of odontogenic inflammatory processes of the maxillofacial system were analyzed.

Within 3 years, 62(48.0%) pregnant women had outpatient appointments with exacerbation of chronic periodontitis. 19(14.5%) women were diagnosed with odontogenic jaw periostitis; 19(14.5%) pregnant women sought the help of a dental surgeon with various inflammatory infiltrations of the maxillofacial area.

In the anamnesis of 86% of women during dental examinations of pregnant women, the examination and treatment were not carried out efficiently, there were "false certificates". According to the results of statistical analysis, it was revealed that out of 128(100%) pregnant women who applied after outpatient surgical interventions, 21(15.8%) women were identified during dynamic follow-up who were hospitalized with various types of purulent-necrotic complications of the maxillofacial region.

Conclusion. Thus, based on the results of the monitoring, it can be concluded that the number of pregnant women applying to a dental surgeon was significantly higher than the total number of patients who applied for medical care. The dentist's tactics provide for constant monitoring of pregnant women and require optimal preventive measures to prevent negative outcomes in the further spread of odontogenic infection of the maxillofacial space.